

DEVELOPMENT OF TOOL SEARCHING SYSTEM FOR TOOL CRIB

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ABSTRACT:

Most of the medium and large scale manufacturing industries have the larger tool room that is used to provide required tool. The tool finding in these rooms is a tedious task and time consuming also. The problem of keeping track of these valuable tools, of knowing where to locate every tool that has been issued, and getting them back promptly after they have been used, is an important task. Various methods are used for this purpose such as, crib ware method, manual method, tool shark method and mobile method. Each of these methods have their own advantages and limitations, This paper discusses development of new tool searching system by executing limitations of existing methods.

1. INTRODUCTION:

A very large number of manufacturing tools such as drills, taps, reamers, are used very frequently also number of different jigs and fixtures, are taken in every manufacturing cycles from the tool room of the industry and returned there after being used. This phenomenon has the problem of keeping record and track of these valuable tools, such as having knowledge of where to locate each tool that has been issued or given for use and taken them back promptly after they have been used.

To address this particular problem a mechanism can be provided to these tool rooms with the help of which it is easier to find needed tool in less time. A database can be provided to tool room so that the management of tools jigs and fixtures can be efficient. Using this database and using a proper sensing system the system can be developed which will give the exact location of the tool.

Zhou Binghai et al Designed a knowledge based decision support system for tool management in flexible manufacturing system, they also took an overview of issues related to tool management that is including tool requirement planning, tool real-time scheduling, tool crib management, tool inventory control, tool fault diagnosis, tool tracking and tool monitoring etc. and finally concluded that the system they have developed has various advantages over other existing systems.

B. Tan Considered a continuous material-flow manufacturing system having an unreliable production system and also a variable demand source that changes randomly between zero to the maximum level. He also investigated two approximately single hedging policies. They have empirically shown that an approximate policy that uses a single hedging level which is the sum of a production uncertainty term and a demand uncertainty term gives accurate results for the expected average cost.

A supply Pro whitepaper Says that for automobile repairing services that seeks cost reduction in repair and maintenance operations, it is very important to streamline the tooling fulfillment process from time of order receipt to the time of return. The paper also says that for reducing cost, repair order cycle time, optimizing labor and improving process management depends upon efficiently organizing tool fulfillment rules and procedures Cribmaster executive whitepaper Says that they can reduce wait times at the crib by 60%-90%, issue and return time can be reduced by 50%-90% and reduced labor cost by 40%-80% only by process improvement. They also exert that the software used by the system typically provide returns cost savings like; reduction in lost tools carrying cost, obsolete inventory, overstock inventory when user applies RFID based Cribmaster system.

'The tool crib of the future' executive whitepaper Concluded that by properly managing indirect material one can increase the effectiveness of various processes, effectively managing inventory can eliminate wasted money on too much on-hand inventory, wasted time searching for tools, wasted man hours searching for inventory, wasted production time when attempting to locate items and wasted money from pilferage and hoarding of inventory.

1.1 MANUAL METHOD

It is a traditional method which is still widely used in various industries. In this system a person who is in search of tool first refers catalogue i.e. list of number of tools present in tool room and its condition of it Also this method includes daily update of tool sign in and sign out. It helps to maintain the data like what tools do we

already have? How much disposable tooling are we consuming? How many tools, cutters and inserts do we need to order? Who is accountable for lost, broken and scrapped tooling? What tools are used for specific part numbers or materials? What tools need to be re-certified for use? Etc.

1.2 CRIB WARE METHOD

This is the simplest method of doing tool management this is done by the use of small brass checks bearing the individual numbers of the men. This uses a tool check board, as shown in figure no 1 below, when a person approaches to tool room for a tool; he gives one of his circular checks provided to him. Tool Keeper then this check on the right-hand pin under the man's name. He then removes one of the 12 rectangular checks, and hangs it on the other pin which is in front of the space from which the tool was taken.

Fig. no.1 Tool check board

1.3 MOBILE METHOD:

In this method Instead of sending workers back to a tool crib, tool cribs are made to come to the workers. These tool cribs can be customized and can be set up directly on jobsite. These tool cribs may have storage and control systems, cabinets and shelving.

1.4 LIMITATIONS OF EXISTING METHODS

- These methods are time consuming.
- They waste working time of technician
- There is a need of trained technician
- Possibility of losing a tool

These limitations create a gap for research and development of new methods for tool searching or tool room management.

2. WORKING OF THE SYSTEM: SOFTWARE:

In our system one want to search for tool needs to enter that tool serial number on the software, then by using serial port signals are sent to microcontroller. After sending that code, software starts the searching appropriate tool. To get the result one should wait for 30 sec. after getting the appropriate tool one should reset the data.

MICROCONTROLLER & INDICATION UNIT:

The project hardware uses 89C51 microcontroller which in configured in serial communication mode (PORT C). The serial part in configured with mode 0, baud rate 9600. The desired machine code is obtained from computer through RS232 serial interface. The data received from the computer is in ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) format. The microcontroller program converts the i/p ASCII code into HEX format & transfers the same to PORT. A 4:16 decoder is connected to PORT. The 4 i/p data line of IC74154 receives the decoded data & enables single output line such than an LED connected to that line is turned ON. This LED is placed at the rack, where the desired tool machine is placed. The LED will remain ON for a period of 30 seconds.

Therefore, the microcontroller program will reset PORT & will wait for next i/p to process. During a wait period of 30 seconds nor data is processed by microcontroller & neither software.

Fig. 2 Block diagram of the tool searching system

Fig 3 Circuit diagram

Fig 4 Power circuit

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3. CONCLUSIONS:

The system is found to be useful in the following sense.

1. This new technology helps to decrease time and efforts for finding tool.
2. It helps to reduce total production time.
3. Tool searching system uses database and is helpful in tool crib where number of tools are more.
4. This system may find its applications in various other areas like shopping centre etc.